

NEW LOW COST TEXTILE PREFORMS AND SHORT CYCLE PROCESSING TECHNIQUES FOR THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY: Weft-inserted warp knitting is chosen for its low production cost to produce a novel thermoplastic textile preform, containing both the non-crimp reinforcing fibres and the thermoplastic matrix ribbons. The composite structures are obtained by simple hot pressing the textile preform without any further addition of the matrix. Special glass sizings and low viscosity matrix materials are developed to ensure a good wetting out of the reinforcement and an easy, thus fast impregnation. This new SPLIT-WARPKNIT structure reveals a high potential for a good mechanical performance while it remains cost-competitive with other commercial materials, already available on the market. An extensive mechanical and physical analysis, of which the evaluation of the impregnation quality and the global fibre distribution, is carried out to determine the optimal processing window for two different fast processing techniques, while the flow of the highly viscous thermoplastic matrix through the fibre bundles is modelled.

KEYWORDS: textile preforms, thermoplastic, glass fibres, fast processing, impregnation quality, flow behaviour, automotive

INTRODUCTION

Improved safety standards and extended luxury demands have tremendously increased the weight of vehicles. With the urge of weight reduction in the automobile industry for minimising fuel consumption and exhaust emissions, fibre reinforced composite materials offer, besides Al and Mg, a significant light weight potential in structural body parts of vehicles [1]. Due to some severe disadvantages of thermoset composites, like high production cycle times, limited recyclability, constrained storage time as well as storage requirements, engineering composites based on thermoplastics have been investigated in recent years. Despite a promising cost decrease when using thermoplastic matrix composites, the price level is far away from that of competing light weight materials, such as Al. A decrease in the fabrication cost of thermoplastic composite parts can be obtained if the separate impregnation step can be eliminated, by means of a 'dry impregnation' [1]. It seems that textile preforms are

particularly well suited due to the experience of the textile industry with low-cost production and optimal textile processes.. Hence a considerable decrease of the part cost is only achieved by significantly lowering the cost of pre-impregnated thermoplastic textile preforms [5].

However, major difficulties are encountered during the processing of thermoplastic matrix composites and include the impregnation due to the high viscosities and low shear flow rates. To overcome these problems, several alternative methods of combining the fibres and the matrix have been developed to reduce the mass transfer distance of the matrix to the fibres during processing , e.g. the use of several types of "combined yarns", where the reinforcing fibres are intensely mixed with the matrix fibres [2]. A new cost-effective thermoplastic textile preform has been developed [3]. The advantages of this new class of thermoplastic split-warpknit textile preform are [4][5]:

- low production cost of the textile structure
- preform shows a good drapability
- increased mechanical properties due to the non-crimp textile structure
- one textile structure is composed of different layers, with different orientations of the reinforcing fibres
- short cycle processing time is possible
- as the hybrid yarn structure determines the homogeneity of the distribution of the reinforcing fibres in the polymer matrix and thus the mechanical performance, a good composite part can be made

SPLIT-WARPKNIT TEXTILE PREFORM

A new thermoplastic textile preform, both containing the reinforcing fibres and the thermoplastic matrix ribbons is developed. The thermoplastic ribbon, which will later form the matrix, is either used as knitting yarn or laid down parallel to the glass fibres, forming a hybrid yarn.

Material Selection

The characteristics required for the novel pre-impregnated textile structure are versatile and demand special research [4][5]. The main requirements are:

- Good compatibility between the reinforcing fibres and the thermoplastic matrix
 - good adhesion
 - good wetting behaviour, giving an overall good impregnation quality
- Low melt viscosity of the polymer matrix to achieve an easy flow during processing
- Good processibility of the film, when using a thermoplastic grade with a high MFI
- Adequate splitting behaviour of the film
- Adequate knitting behaviour of fibres and matrix ribbons

A thorough market survey pointed out that the commercially available thermoplastic films are not suited for composite applications. They do not contain the required antioxidants, stabilisers and coupling agents and are often coated. The glass fibres were also not available with the suited sizings for good adhesion and textile processing and of necessary fineness.

Therefore, special glass sizings and low viscosity PP matrix materials were selected and modified in a laboratory scale aimed at a good wetting of the glass fibres and an easy impregnation. After optimization, a commercially available PP grade (Shell XS 6500 S) has been stabilized and modified with a maleic anhydride grafted PP during film extrusion.

The glass fibres with the optimized sizing have been produced by Glasseiden GmbH Oschatz, Germany as cost-effective direct roving of 300 tex fineness. The material selection and development of PET-matrices and corresponding sized glass fibres revealed continuous amorphous film of Hoechst AG best suited for the new processing technique. PET-compatible glass fibres have been also produced by Glasseiden GmbH Oschatz, Germany.

Textile Preform

Weft-inserted warp knitting is selected to produce the split-warpknit textile preform [4][5] (see fig 1 and 2).

Figure 1: Warp knitting with weft inserts

Figure 2: Split-warpknit textile

During the first knitting trials of a *co-knitted split-warpknit* uni-axial structure, where the matrix ribbons are knitted around glass fibres (fig 3), several problems occurred:

- a polymer mixture with a high MFI (10 times more than commercially used) was taken to produce the film
- the film was not oriented in the width direction
- the film showed a high brittleness
- the thermoplastic tape has a too low elongation
- the low resistance of the ribbons lead to untwisting and tearing of the tapes
- during rewinding of the bobbins the stretch ratio in the length direction increased
- the glass rovings were too heavy and too open to use a E 18 gaugeknitting machine: a change to 12 needles per inch was necessary
- tubular guides had to be used for the glass rovings
- the production of the glass beams should be eliminated by using creels

After evaluation of the produced composite laminates, more questions arose that were linked to further material optimisation. The insufficient composite properties could be due to bad wetting of the fibres or due to the bad impregnation homogeneity caused by the textile structure. However, the kinetics of wetting single fibres by thermoplastic melts showed immediate wetting of the sized glass fibres, in contrary, the co-knitted textile structure, with

the thermoplastic ribbons knitted around the glass fibres, resulted in a composite material with a highly non-uniform fibre distribution surrounded with unreinforced matrix rich zones. Hence lower mechanical properties were obtained. One possibility to improve the impregnation homogeneity is to reduce the flow path by using of a new textile structure where the thermoplastic ribbons are inserted in the glass fibre bundles, forming a hybrid yarn, and sewed together with a non-meltable stitching yarn. This led to the hybrid split-warpknit material where the thermoplastic ribbons are laid down parallel to the glass fibre bundles and a PET stitching yarn is used to form the textile preform (fig 4). Another preform is now being developed where a meltable, compatible stitching yarn is used.

Figure 3: Co-knitted split-warpknit

Figure 4: Hybrid split-warpknit

Short Cycle Processes

Given the apparent potential for the application of thermoplastic fabric composites in high volume manufacturing, the conflicting demands of process cycle time and laminate quality require to be resolved.

In all material developments, focusing on mass applications, the processability under industrial conditions, is an important issue. When considering thermoplastic composites, the minimum cycle time to consolidate the preform is of primary importance [4].

The process cycle involves preheating the matrix polymer above its melting point, followed by a compaction to wet out the reinforcement and cooling the laminate to below the polymer crystallisation temperature [2]. Before the matrix will flow it must be heated sufficiently above its melting point to reduce the viscosity for full fibre impregnation. While overheating will degrade the polymer, the preheating stage is critical and can be achieved in two ways.

In the classical hot pressing *in-mould heating and cooling* method, a loose stack of textile layers is placed in a cold mould, heated, pressed and cooled down in the mould to produce a pre-compacted sheet. It involves high heating energy flow to and from the forming equipment, resulting in longer cycle times and higher operating costs. This classical process is hence far too expensive for industrial use. During an alternative production method, the fabric is preheated separately in an external oven prior transfer to the forming equipment, which is at a temperature below T_g . This technique is well established in the traditional *GMT processing* and eliminates the need to cycle the mould temperature, avoiding large cycle times. The major difference between processing continuous reinforced materials and classical GMTs is that generally no bulk or large scale flow is thought to occur [2].

Highly oriented thermoplastic split-film ribbons will, when heated up, shrink considerably. So, it is necessary to support the textile preform throughout the heating phase to prevent an uncontrolled shrinkage and curling of the fabric. Note that the classical GMT process does not fulfil this requirement. Hence, alternative processing techniques have to be developed for the fast and cost-effective composite production when using the new thermoplastic split-warpknit textile preform.

Quicktemp Concept

In the alternative method, the mould has to go through the same thermal history as the part, which immediately poses a heat transfer problem. Conventional moulds are usually made of steel and it is virtually impossible to cool them down in a sufficiently short time. An improvement can be obtained using diaphragma forming, which is however expensive due to the use of special film material.

A new concept for cycle time reduction has been conceived [4][5]:

1. The surface temperature of the mould on the cavity side is the quantity of primary interest to the part. Other domains of the mould can be kept at a different temperature.
2. A large temperature difference between two media (or two domains of one mould) can be used to enhance the heat transfer.
3. The duration of the heating phase is the bottleneck when optimising the cycle time. Water cooling of the composite is fast enough.

This concept has been incorporated in a new mould design. The mould is mainly made of a material with a low temperature conductivity (steel) while only the small part, close to the mould surface, consists of a material with a high temperature conductivity. The first region is held at a very high temperature and acts as a heat storage while the second region, equipped with heating and cooling systems to adjust the temperature, is the forming region and is in contact with the part. During the heating phase, additional heat is flowing from the heat storage into the forming region due to the large temperature gradient.

Adapted GMT Process

To reduce the cycle times, the idea rose to modify the GMT process (Glass mat reinforced thermoplastics), where the pile of textile layers is externally heated and transferred to a mould at constant temperature below the melting temperature of the thermoplastic matrix. If the mould is kept at a low temperature, cycle time is reduced drastically because the heating and the cooling of the massive equipment is no longer needed [4].

However, any alteration of the ideal, uneconomical hot pressing method has an influence on the impregnation and distribution of the fibres throughout the composite. While in the classical process the impregnation time is a programmable parameter, this is no longer the case for the GMT based production process.

Problems also rise during the external heating and transfer of the pile of molten textile layers from the oven to the press. Because a loose stack of split-warpknit textile layers contains about 80% of air, the stack of textiles should be precompacted to remove as much air as possible in order to accelerate the heating. During convective heating trials it was observed that the textile exhibited a high amount of shrinkage, preferentially in one direction, distorting

the fibre architecture and resulting in an uncontrolled waviness of the fibres. To provide a degree of constraint, the loose pile of textiles was heated by conduction between two steel platens of a hot press, where teflon sheets were used to prevent sticking of the molten layers to the platens. In industry however, it is possible to precompact the loose stack of textile layers with a kind of calendaring rolls in a continuous way. The actual preheating could be carried out by radiative heating in an inert atmosphere to prevent the oxidation and degradation of the textiles. If radiative heating can be applied, the composite can be produced without the use of Teflon foils. It is also worth trying to use a mould with a lower thermal conductivity to slow down the cooling speed and further improve the impregnation.

MECHANICAL TEST DATA FOR DIFFERENT PROCESSING TECHNIQUES

Classical Hot Pressing

Before going into the different short cycle processes, laminates were manufactured using various split-warpcnit textile preforms with the classical hot pressing technique, resulting in optimal mechanical properties.

Two different types of a glass fibre reinforced polypropylene split-warpcnit textile preform were examined:

1. *co-knitted split-warpcnit* preform where the thermoplastic matrix ribbons are knitted around the glass fibre bundles: mono-axial and bi-axial structure
2. *hybrid split-warpcnit* preform where the thermoplastic matrix ribbons are laid down parallel to the glass fibres and sewed together with a PET yarn: mono-axial structure

The properties are also compared to "Twintex" based material.

The mono-axial hybrid split-warpcnit preform has a higher fibre volume fraction than the mono-axial co-knitted split-warpcnit preform but analogous tensile properties (table 1).

The bending properties of the hybrid split-warpcnit laminates are significantly better than those of the co-knitted split-warpcnit laminates, probably due to the more homogeneous fibre distribution. No matrix rich zones, which could cause interlaminar shear failure during transversal three point bending are present in the new hybrid split-warpcnit preform structure. The properties of the new split-warpcnits are well comparable to the ones of competitive co-mingled yarns, already commercially available (Twintex).

Adapted GMT Process

The main goal of this study was to investigate whether it is possible to use a GMT based production process for the split film co-knitted composites. Furthermore, an optimisation of the production parameters was carried out. Considering the process of external heating under slight pressure, transferring the molten material to the cold mould and consolidating under pressure, several parameters are examined:

Preheating temperature and heating method
Mould temperature
Pressure of consolidation
Holding time at pressure

Table 1: Tensile properties of the first and the second generation split-warpcnit laminates, compared to Twintex co-mingled yarn (Vetrotex). Processing parameters (optimal classical cycle): 25 bar, 220°C during 5 min

	Mono-axial co-knitted	Mono-axial hybrid	Bi-axial co-knitted	Bi-axial hybrid	Twintex TPP 60650
Fibre volume fraction (%)	22	37	39	36	46
Tensile strength (MPa)	297*	289*	360**	320**	317*
Young's modulus (GPa)	14.5*	16.5*	18**	17.5**	16.6*

*: related to a fibre volume fraction of 20%

** : related to a fibre volume fraction of 40%

The experimental results showed that the only parameter of major importance for the tensile behaviour of cross ply laminates of the bi-axial co-knitted split-warpcnit textile, where the matrix ribbons are knitted around the glass fibres, oriented in the 0° and 90° direction, was the *preheating temperature*, the temperature to which the material is externally heated in an oven before it is transferred to the press to be formed in a cold mould. This temperature greatly influences the viscosity of the thermoplastic matrix and hence the ease of wetting out and flow through the closely packed fibre bundles. This is even more pronounced when studying the shear modulus during ±45 tensile tests (fig 5). The pressure and the mould temperature influence the shear modulus to a lower extent.

Figure 5: The influence of the preheating temperature on the shear properties of cross ply laminates of the bi-axial co-knitted split-warpcnit, tested at 45°. The shear modulus is given

$$by: G_{xy} = \frac{E_{45}}{2(1 + \nu_{xy})}$$

The optimal process parameter set is:

- Pre heating temperature = 280°C
- Mould temperature = 125°C
- Pressure = 48 bar
- Holding time = 300 sec.

resulting in optimal mechanical properties for GMT-produced bi-axial co-knitted split-warpknit aminates :

- Tensile modulus: 15.92 GPa
- Tensile strength: 305.4 MPa
- Shear modulus: 0.69 GPa
- $\pm 45^\circ$ tensile modulus: 2.17 GPa
- Poisson coefficient: 0.58

The optimal properties for the conventional hot pressing method and the adapted GMT processing technique are compared in table 2 for cross ply symmetric laminates of the bi axial co-knitted split-warpknit textile.

The lowest void fraction and the highest fibre volume fraction is found for the classical production cycle, resulting in a better impregnation homogeneity and thus an overall better mechanical performance of the composite. However, the classical production cycle is much more time consuming and economically non-competitive and further optimisation of the adapted GMT process is still possible.

Table 2: Comparison of the mechanical properties of the biaxial co-knitted split-warpknit

	<i>Hot pressing</i>	<i>Adapted GMT</i>
Fibre volume fraction (%)	48.0	46.6
Void fraction (%)	3.2	5.4
Matrix volume fraction (%)	48.8	48
Tensile strength (corrected to 50% fibre volume fraction) (MPa)	361.5	327.3
Tensile modulus (corrected to 50% fibre volume fraction) (GPa)	21.25	17.06
Shear modulus: $\pm 45^\circ$ tensile testing(GPa)	1.73	0.69

Prototype Development

A dome-type part has been manufactured with a lab-scale mould, using the "Quicktemp" principle. Figure 6 shows a shoesole, produced with an adapted GMT process, using existing industrial equipment. These preliminary prototype trials could already show the industrial processability of the new thermoplastic split-warpknit preform.

An industrial tool for the production of an automotive upper washer spring seat has been recently manufactured incorporating the new "Quicktemp" fast heating concept (see fig 7). This tool will be operated in an industrial environment.

Figure 6: Shoesole, GMT, bi-axial co-knitted split-warpknit

Figure 7: "Quicktemp" mould for upper washer spring seat

Modelling of the Impregnation

The main issue during the production of thermoplastic composites is the impregnation, controlled by the velocity and the ease of flow of the thermoplastic matrix through the closely packed fibre bundles.

The flow of a polymer matrix through a regular array of reinforcing fibre bundles is often described by Darcy's law as a flow through a porous medium [8][9][12]:

$$q_i = \frac{K_{ij}}{\mu} \frac{\partial p}{\partial x_j} \quad (1)$$

with K_{ij} the permeability tensor and μ the viscosity.

While the permeability tensor is mostly experimentally determined, the capillary model is one of the mostly used geometric approaches to calculate the permeability of a porous medium, given by the Carman-Kozeny equation [6][7][8][12]. However, because this equation is developed for a packed bed of ellipsoids, the permeability is isotropic which can not be valid for a UD reinforcement where the transverse flow is much more difficult than the flow along the fibre bundles. Gutowski et al. did propose a modified equation which forces the transverse permeability (K becomes anisotropic) to approach zero as the fibre volume fraction reaches a theoretical maximum value, depending on the stacking pattern of the fibres [9][12][14].

While Darcy's law for the flow through a porous medium is a good model to describe the relative flow of a low viscous thermoset matrix through a regular array of fibre bundles, it can not be valid for modelling the flow in thermoplastic matrix composites. The flow under pressure of the melted thermoplastic matrix through the reinforcing fibres, should be modelled as a squeeze flow of a viscous, compressible medium [10][11].

Since in the *conventional hot pressing*, a sufficiently high pressure is already applied during the heating phase, the stacked textile layers are strongly compacted before the polymer melts and the originally round fibre bundles become elliptical. When however, the material is externally heated (*GMT like process*), the molten polymer will surround the fibre bundles and under influence of the surface tension force them to take up a circular cross section..

The model, which is currently under development, predicts the impregnation quality as a function of the production parameters and can be subdivided in three different levels [14]:

1. a *micro scale model*, where the fibre diameter is a typical length unit. The description of the flow on a micro scale, allows to trace the influence of deviations of the ideal stacking pattern of the fibres (missing of a fibre, displacement with regard to the ideal stacking, variation in fibre diameter...), on the permeability.
2. an *intermediate scale model*, where the fibre bundle diameter is chosen as a typical length. The radial flow in the fibre bundles is described by the equation of Brinkman and the permeability is given by Gebart [13][14]. For the flow along the fibre bundles, the equations of Navier Stokes are used.
3. a *macro scale model*, where the length unit is much larger than the bundle diameter and where the reinforcement can be considered as a continuous porous medium.

However, the development will be focused on the micro and intermediate scale model.

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REFERENCES

1. Singkofer R. Mehn R., "Advanced Thermoplastic Composites based on Knitted Fabrics with Weft Insertion - Economical Application in High Load Vehicle Components", Proc. 17th Intern Sampe Conference, Basel, Switzerland, May 28-30 1996.
2. Wakeman M.D., Cain T.A., Rudd C.M., "Optimisation of the Flexural Stiffness of Compression Moulded Co-mingled Glass and Polypropylene Composites, Proc. ECCM 7, London, May 14-16, 1996
3. Mäder E., "New Hybrid Yarns for Continuous Fibre-reinforced Thermoplastics", Proc 35th Intern man-Made Fibres Congress, Dornbirn, Austria, September 25-27, 1996

4. Stumpf H., Mäder E., Baeten S., Pisanikovski T., Zäh W., Eng K., Andersson C.-H., Verpoest I., Schulte K., "New Thermoplastic Composite Preforms based on Split-film Warp Knitting", Proc. TexComp Conf, Aachen, Germany, December 9-11, 1996
5. Stumpf H., Mäder E., Schulte K., Zäh W., "New Thermoplastic Composites Made from Low-cost Textile Preforms and Specialized Processing Techniques for Short Cycle Times", Proc. 17th Intern? Sampe Conference, Basel, Switzerland, May 28-30, 1996
6. Ye L., Klinkmüller V., Friedrich K.: Impregnation and Consolidation in Composites made of GF/PP Powder Impregnated Bundles, Journal of Thermoplastic Composite Materials, vol 5, p 32-48, 1992
7. Seo J.W., Lee W.I.: A Model of the Resin Impregnation of Thermoplastic Composites, Journal of Composite Materials, vol 25, p 1127-1142, September 1991
8. PP, Structure, Blends and Composites, Vol 3, Composites, edited by J. Karger-Kocsis, Chapman and Hall, 1995
9. Klinkmüller V., Um M.K., Friedrich K., Kim B.S.: Impregnation and Consolidation of different GF/PP Commingled Yarns, Proc. of ICCM-10, Whistler B.C., Canada, August 1995, vol III, p 397-404
10. Balasubramanyam R., Jones R.S, Wheeler A.B.: Modelling Transverse Flows of Reinforced Thermoplastic Materials, Composites vol 20, no 1, p 33-37, January 1989
11. Ranganathan S., Advani S.G., Lamontia M.A.: A Non-isothermal Process Model for Consolidation and Void Reduction during In-situ Tow Placement of Thermoplastic Composites, Journal of Composite Materials, vol 29 no 8, p 1040-1061, 1995
12. Vol 10, Composite Materials Series: Flow and Rheology in Polymer Matrix Composites Manufacturing, Editor Suresh G. Advani, Series Editor R.B. Pipes, Elsevier, 1995
13. Gebart B.R.: Permeability of Unidirectional Reinforcements for RTM, Journal of Composite Materials, vol 26, no 8, p 110-1133, 1992
14. Lundström T.S., Gebart B.R.: Effect of Perturbation of Fibre Architecture on Permeability inside Fibre Tows, Journal of Composite Materials, vol 29, no 4, p 424-443, 1995